

THE IMPACT OF MASCULINITY NORMS ON MENTAL HEALTH OF MEN: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

¹Dr. Sarah Mufti, ²Sana Mirza

¹Department of Psychology, University of Gujrat

²Department of Psychology, University of Gujrat

sarah.mufti@uog.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Article History

Received on 27 July 2025

Accepted on 28 Aug 2025

Published on 29 Aug 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

In recent years, concerns have grown around the mental health of men and the role that masculinity norms may play in exacerbating psychological distress. This study examined the influence of masculinity on men's mental health by focusing on depression, stress, anxiety, suicidal ideation, and self-efficacy among youth in Pakistan. Utilizing a sample of 1,256 participants aged 13 to 25, including both males and females, the research investigates how traditional gender roles and societal expectations affect mental well-being. Findings indicated significant gender-based differences in moral disengagement and masculinity scores, with males reporting higher levels, which are positively correlated with indicators of psychological distress. The results call for culturally-sensitive interventions and a critical reassessment of prevailing masculinity norms in mental health discourse.

Introduction

In the context of Pakistani society, masculinity is often shaped by deeply rooted cultural, religious, and familial norms. These societal expectations define men as stoic, emotionally resilient, and dominant, often discouraging them from expressing vulnerability or seeking psychological help. Although these traits are culturally reinforced as ideal masculine behavior, they may inadvertently contribute to adverse mental health outcomes. With the rise of depression, anxiety, and suicide rates among young Pakistani men, it becomes essential to examine how these masculine norms are influencing mental health.

Globally, men are less likely than women to seek mental health treatment (Mahalik et al., 2003). In Pakistan, where mental health awareness is already limited and stigmatized, this disparity is even more pronounced. Traditional masculine norms not only suppress emotional expression but also associate help-seeking with weakness, a trait contrary to the ideal masculine image (Courtenay, 2000). This study addresses these concerns by quantitatively examining the impact of masculinity on mental health, using validated scales to assess constructs like depression, anxiety, suicidal ideation, and self-efficacy.

Masculinity norms are the social norms that are expected from the male in their roles, behaviors and relationships so that men are acting or spending their life accordingly with these societal norms. It's not innate or biologically fixed but shaped by our society and culture (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005). Mostly in our society masculinity norms are dominance, emotional restrictiveness, avoidance of femininity, toughness, negative toward sexual minority, importance of sex, self-reliance also impact on mental health as it may cause depression, stress, anxiety, depression and also generate thoughts about suicide (Wong et al., 2017).

As we study deeply get a great knowledge through Gender role Conflict Theory, this theory suggest that when men is forced to follow these social norms they may mental health problems and mostly they can't go to psychologist for their mental health issues (O'Neil, 2008). The societal expectation of men to be tough, self-reliant, emotional restrictiveness and to avoid femininity may results in depression and also lead to avoid treatment seeking in men (Johnson et al., 2012). Depression in men are underreported as men don't seek any help from mental health professionals. A finding from a national survey reveals that 9% of men experience daily symptoms of anxiety and depression and only less than half (41%) go for treatment when needed (Blumberg et al., 2015). Adolescents, men belong to a lower family

status or with dark colors don't receive any treatment or only when they need it badly (Cummings et al., 2014).

Masculinity norms are directly affecting the mental health of men and they aren't seeking any help. The unrealistic masculinity norms expectation may results in effected psychological outcomes. It create masculinity strains. Winning the status like to achieve goals in their life may lead to positive outcomes like less substance abuse, seek for treatment or good diet more studies are needed to understand what masculinity norms that are risky and those that are good for effective mental health issues (Salgado et al., 2019). Substance abuse, anger, irritability are the external depressive symptoms that are found in men but these symptoms are not completely define depression in men because sometimes these are the behavior of men (Call & Shafer, 2018).

The Dysfunctional Strain Paradigm is helpful to understand that pressure to show or confirm masculinity norms men commit suicide. It show that when men are unable to confirm masculinity norms or meet the ideals of masculinity norms they face anxiety, depression and suicidal idealization (Addis, 2003). In the past decade, suicide is becoming normal cause of death. Traditional masculinity norms like emotional restrictiveness, toughness, self-reliant, dominance and avoidance of femininity are linked to poor mental health conditions also links with suicide (Pirkis et al., 2019). Norms like toughness, emotional control are gender traits that are the part of hegemonic masculinity (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005).

In addition masculinity norms also shape how men think and deal with their mental health issue. (Martin et al., 2013) says that men show more symptoms of depression than women as substance abuse, irritability than internalized symptoms of depression as sadness, weakness etc. According to (Levant, 2020) high level to follow masculinity norms may lead to high level of anxiety and depressive symptoms. When the demand arises from the person capacity it may results in stress.

This study sheds light on rigid masculine norms negatively impact men's mental health, particularly in a country like Pakistan where discussing emotional struggles is often stigmatized. By exploring the relationship between masculinity ideals especially muscularity concerns and mental health outcomes among male students from schools, colleges and universities, the research fill a critical gap in local literature where such issues are underexplored. Additionally,

the findings would help mental health professionals, educators and policy makers develop gender sensitive interventions and awareness programs tailored to the unique challenges faced by Pakistani men.

Methodology

Sample

Sample consisted of study consisted of adolescents and adults from different schools, colleges and university of different cities of district Gujrat. The relevant authorities were approached and permission of data collection was taken from them. Then, 1256 participants were engaged and they were being explained the purpose of the research and took informed consent for their participation. After that they completed demographic sheet along with the other questionnaires of muscularity norms, anxiety, stress, depression, and suicidal ideation. They were ensured about the confidentiality of their information.

Inclusion Criteria

Participant included in this study comprised both males and females within the range of 13 to 25 years. Only individuals with no prior history of psychological disorders considered for participation. This criterion ensured that the sample represented a psychologically healthy population within specified age group.

Exclusion Criteria

Participant who identified as a transgender or gay were excluded from the study. Additionally, individuals who submitted uncompleted survey or experiences any psychological problem were not included in the sample. This was done to maintain the consistency and reliability of the collected data.

Instruments

Masculinity Role Norm Inventory- Short Form (MRNI-SF)

It was developed by (Levant et al., 2013) MRNI-SF is a 21 item scale that assesses adherence to traditional masculinity norms across domains as restrictive emotionality, self-reliance, toughness, dominance, avoidance of femininity, negative toward sexual minority and importance of sex. Item number 15, 16 and 21 cover restrictive emotionality, item number 6, 7, and 14 cover self-reliance, item number 1, 5 and 13 cover negative toward sexual minority, item number 4, 8 and 10 cover avoidance of femininity, item number 9, 11 and 18 cover importance of sex, item number 2, 3 and 12 cover dominance and item number 17, 19 and 20

cover toughness. High score represented traditional masculinity norms in an individual. Reliability of the scale was calculated using Cronbach's alpha which .89 is. 7-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree, 7=Strongly Agree) is used in this scale.

Center for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale (CES-D)

The CES-D (Radloff, 1977) is a 20 item self-report scale assessing depressive symptoms in general population. It has a reliability ranging from .85-.90. The scale consisted of 4- point Likert scale (1=rarely or none of the times to 4=most of the times). High scores indicate depression in individual. In this scale item number 4, 8, 12 and 16 are positive symptoms so they are reverse scoring.

Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)

Developed (Cohen, et al., 1983) the PSS is 10-item scale used to measure perceived level of stress over the past month. There are two sub-scales of perceived stress scale. Perceived helplessness (item 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, 10) that measure an individual's lack of control on their own emotions and reactions. Lack of self-efficacy (item 4, 5, 7, 8) that measure an individual's inability to handle problems. High score results in stress in person. Reliability: Cronbach's alpha= .84. Scale= 5-point Likert scale (0=never to 4=very often)

Anxiety Control Questionnaire (ACQ)

The ACQ (Rapee et al., 1996) is a 30-item scale that measure perceived control over anxiety-related events and symptoms. This scale covers internal and external reactions. External reaction forward score items are 1, 12, 19, 29, and reverse score items are 2, 5, 7, 8, 14, 15, 16, 20, 23, 24, 25, 30. Internal reaction forward score items are 4, 10, 11, 13, 17, 21, 22, 27 and reverse score items are 3, 6, 9, 18, 26, 28. High score represents high level of anxiety. Reliability: Cronbach's alpha= .86. Scale: 6-point Likert Scale (0= Strongly Disagree to 5= Strongly Agree)

Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale

The SIDAS (Van Spijker et al., 2014) is a 5-items tool for assessing suicidal thoughts their frequency controllability and impact. High scores shows high level of suicidal thoughts. Reliability: Cronbach's alpha= .91. Scale: 10-point Likert Scale (0= not at all to 10= extremely)

Procedure

Data were collected using survey method. Participants were approached in person of schools, colleges and university based on convenience and permission from relevant authorities. A printed questionnaire was distributed which included: A cover page that describe the purpose

of study, consent form, demographic information form, five validated psychological scales: Masculinity Norm Inventory Scale-Short Form (MRNI-SF), Center for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale (CES-D), Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), Anxiety Control Questionnaire (ACQ), Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale (SIDAS).

Participants were given ample minutes to complete the forms in a quiet, designed area. Completed surveys were collected immediately to ensure data integrity and prevent loss. Data were later manually entered into SPSS software for analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Participant were given informed consent and were communicated about the voluntary nature of the study. Confidentiality and anonymity were assured. The data were stored securely with access limited to researcher.

Results

Table-1 *Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N=1256)*

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent	M	SD
Age				17.42	3.02
Academic Achievement				71.65	14.86
Gender	Female	640	51		
	Male	616	49		
Socioeconomic Status	High	95	7.6		
	Middle	1066	84.9		
	Low	95	7.6		
Institute	School	498	39.6		
	College	348	27.7		
	University	410	32.6		
Education Level	7	134	10.7		
	8	169	13.5		
	9	103	8.2		
	10	93	7.4		
	11	208	16.6		
	12	138	11		
	13	143	11.4		

		14	66	5.3
		15	76	6.1
		16	126	10
Residence	Rural	564	44.9	
	Urban	692	55.1	
Family Status	Nuclear	792	63.1	
	Joint	464	36.9	

Table no. 1 presented the demographic data of 1,256 participants in this study. The number of male and female were almost equal with 51% female and 49% male. The majority of participants were enrolled in university (32.6%) followed by school (39.6%) and college (27.7%).

Table-2 Correlation among Masculinity Norms and Various Mental Health Variables

Sr no.	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	Masculinity	-	-.16**	0.03	.16**	-.18**	.14**	.13**	.11**	.16**
2	SIDAS		-	-.15**	-.22**	.11**	-0.05	-0.05	-.26**	-.19**
3	Stress			-	.79**	.27**	.07**	0.04	.27**	-0.03
4	PH				-	-.42**	.19**	.17**	.32**	-0.05
5	LSE					-	-.17**	-.19**	-.10**	0.03
6	ACQE						-	.73**	.14**	-0.04
7	ACQI							-	.13**	-0.01
8	Depression								-	.07**
9	Gender									-

Note: * = $p < 0.5$, ** $p < 0.01$, SIDAS=Suicidal ideation Attribution Scale, PH=Perceived helplessness, LSE=Lack of Self-efficacy, ACQE=Anxiety Control Questionnaire Externalizing, ACQI=Anxiety Control Questionnaire Internalizing.

This table showed statistically strong correlation between various mental health variables and masculinity norms with $p < 0.01$ although the weak magnitude is weak.

Table-3 Gender Differences for Psychological Variables

Variable	Male		Female		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	95% CI (LL, UL)
	M	SD	M	SD			
Masculinity	4.94	1.07	4.64	0.82	-5.59	.001	(-0.41, -0.20)
SIDAS Total	30.87	12.39	35.64	11.61	6.98	.001	(3.41, 6.07)
PH	13.09	5.06	13.63	5.22	1.85	.065	(-0.03, 1.11)
LSE	7.13	3.61	6.91	3.49	-1.12	.265	(-0.62, 0.17)
ACQE	42.45	10.16	43.16	9.54	1.26	.207	(-0.39, 1.80)
ACQI	39.33	11.24	39.57	10.19	0.41	.686	(-0.94, 1.43)
Depression	43.99	8.88	42.57	9.22	-2.77	.006	(-2.42, -0.41)

Note: SIDAS=Suicidal ideation Attribution Scale, PH=Perceived helplessness, LSE=Lack of Self-efficacy, ACQE=Anxiety Control Questionnaire Externalizing, ACQI=Anxiety Control Questionnaire Internalizing.

The table showed that men reported higher masculinity conformity as compared to women ($p < .001$). Women reported more suicidal Ideation (SIDAS) than men ($p < .001$) although men reported higher depression compared to women. All the other variables do not show significant differences.

Table-4 Mean Difference Across Institutes on Masculinity Norms, Suicidal Thoughts, Perceived Helplessness, Lack of Self-Efficacy, External Anxiety, Internal Anxiety and Depression.

Variable	School n=488		College n=348		University n=410		<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
Masculinity	4.96	1.11	4.67	0.89	4.7	0.8	12.51	.001
SIDAS	29.4	13.36	34.77	11.37	36.74	10.03	47.24	.001
PH	12.73	5.42	13.45	4.78	14.07	5.04	7.72	.001
LSE	7.4	3.83	6.78	3.49	6.78	3.21	4.49	0.01
ACQE	43.65	10.17	42.05	10.02	42.47	9.26	3.1	0.04
ACQI	41.26	10.79	38.52	11.33	38.07	9.77	12.05	.001
Depression	43.37	9.05	44.72	8.18	41.96	9.66	8.99	.001

Note=SIDAS=Suicidal ideation Attribution Scale, PH=Perceived helplessness, LSE=Lack of Self-efficacy, ACQE=Anxiety Control Questionnaire Externalizing, ACQI=Anxiety Control Questionnaire Internalizing.

This table showed that potential differences in psychological constructs across educational levels where suicidal ideations and perceived helplessness showed highest in university students and lowest in school students. School students showed lower self-esteem than college or university students. College students showed the higher depression level as compared to university students.

Table-5 Post Hoc Test Across Institutes On Masculinity Norms , Suicidal Thoughts , Perceived Helplessness, Lack Of Self-Efficacy , External Anxiety, Internal Anxiety And Depression.

Variable						95% CI	
	i	j	ij	S.E	p	Lower	Upper
Muscularity	School	College	0.29*	0.07	< .001	0.16	0.42
	School	University	0.26*	0.06	< .001	0.14	0.39
	College	University	-0.03	0.07	0.667	-0.17	0.11
SIDAS	School	College	-5.36*	0.82	< .001	-6.98	-3.75
	School	University	-7.34*	0.79	< .001	-8.89	-5.8
	College	University	-1.98*	0.86	0.022	-3.67	-0.29
PH	School	College	-0.72*	0.36	0.046	-1.42	-0.01
	School	University	-1.34*	0.34	< .001	-2.01	-0.67
	College	University	-0.62	0.37	0.096	-1.36	0.11
LSE	School	College	0.61*	0.25	0.014	0.13	1.1
	School	University	0.62*	0.24	0.009	0.15	1.08
	College	University	0	0.26	0.988	-0.51	0.51
ACQE	School	College	1.60*	0.69	0.02	0.25	2.95
	School	University	1.18	0.66	0.072	-0.11	2.47
	College	University	-0.42	0.72	0.558	-1.83	0.99
ACQI	School	College	2.74*	0.74	< .001	1.29	4.2
	School	University	3.20*	0.71	< .001	1.8	4.59
	College	University	0.45	0.77	0.56	-1.07	1.97

Depression	School	College	-1.35*	0.63	0.033	-2.59	-0.11
	School	University	1.44*	0.6	0.017	0.25	2.62
	College	University	2.78*	0.66	< .001	1.49	4.08

Note * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ SIDAS=Suicidal ideation Attribution Scale, PH=Perceived helplessness, LSE=Lack of Self-efficacy, ACQE=Anxiety Control Questionnaire Externalizing, ACQI=Anxiety Control Questionnaire Internalizing.

Mental health challenges increase with educational level. School students tend to show higher self-efficacy and fewer symptoms of internalizing/externalizing problems. Muscularity perception is lower in school students. Differences between College and University are generally smaller and often not significant.

Figure-1 Mean of masculinity mean of total across institutes

Figure 1 line graph showing the mean scores of perceived masculinity across education levels. School students perceived significantly higher masculinity scores than college and university students. College and university students score are not significantly differ.

Figure-2 Mean of SIDAS total across institute

Figure 2 shows mean SIDAS scores across School, college and university participants. University students reported significantly higher suicidal ideation compared to both school and college students, with school students showing the lowest scores.

Figure-3 Mean of perceived helplessness across educational levels

Figure 3 shows Mean perceived helplessness across educational levels. University students reported highest level of helplessness, followed by college students with school students reporting the lowest levels. Significant difference was found between school and other two groups.

Figure-4 Mean of lack of self- efficacy across educational levels

Figure 4 shows Mean of lack of self- efficacy across educational levels. School students reported highest level of lack of self-efficacy, followed by college and university students. No significant difference was found between college and university participants.

Figure-5 Mean of ACQ externalizing across educational levels

Figure 5 shows Mean of ACQ externalizing across educational levels. School students reported highest level of control of external factors anxiety, followed by university students and with lowest control of external anxiety in college students. Significant difference was found between college and university participants.

Figure-6 Mean of ACQ internalizing across educational levels

Figure 6 shows Mean of ACQ internalizing across educational levels. School students reported highest level of control of internal factors anxiety, followed by college students and with lowest control of internal anxiety in university students. Significant difference was found between college and university participants.

Figure-7 Mean of Depression across educational levels

Figure 7 shows Mean of Depression across educational levels. College students reported highest level of Depression, followed by school students and with lowest level of depression in university students. Significant difference was found between school and university participants.

Discussion

The objective of this study was to explore how various psychological variables including masculinity perception, suicidal ideation, perceived stress, anxiety, and depression differ across educational levels: school, college and university. The analysis involved test for homogeneity for variance, one-way ANOVA post hoc comparison using LSD method. The result yield several meaningful interpretations and implications about developmental and educational transitions.

The sample included 616 male participants, across school, college, and university levels. The mean masculinity score among men was 4.94 (SD = 1.07), indicating a moderately high endorsement of masculinity norms. This suggests that traditional gender roles may still be internalized among young men in the population studied, a critical point given the evolving discourse around male identity and vulnerability.

Correlational analyses revealed significant associations between masculinity and key mental health outcomes. Higher masculinity was negatively associated with suicidal ideation ($r = -.16$, $p < .01$) and low self-esteem ($r = -.18$, $p < .01$), and positively correlated with psychological health ($r = .16$, $p < .01$) and coping strategies (ACQE: $r = .14$, ACQI: $r = .13$). These findings suggest that masculinity, when measured as a norm or trait, may serve as a protective factor in some dimensions of male mental health. However, this should not be interpreted uncritically. While traditional masculinity may bolster confidence and perceived control (reflected in higher psychological health and coping), it may also suppress emotional expression, leading to underreporting of distress. The positive correlation with depression ($r = .11$, $p < .01$), although modest, suggests potential internalized conflict—where traditional male norms restrict help-seeking behaviors, ultimately exacerbating emotional burdens.

Independent samples t-tests showed significant gender differences in masculinity ($t = -5.59$, $p < .001$), with males scoring higher than females. Importantly, males also reported higher depression scores ($M = 43.99$, $SD = 8.88$) than females ($M = 42.57$), which is a notable deviation from global trends where females typically report higher depression. This pattern may be reflective of internalized masculinity norms restricting emotional vulnerability, thus contributing to unresolved mental distress in men. Further, men reported significantly lower

SIDAS scores ($M = 30.87$) compared to females ($M = 35.64$), which may reflect either genuine differences in ideation or masking due to masculine socialization that discourages disclosure of suicidal thoughts.

Results of analysis of variances indicated that school-level males reported significantly higher masculinity scores compared to college and university males. This could reflect developmental and contextual differences—younger males in school may conform more rigidly to normative gender roles, whereas older students might begin challenging or redefining masculinity in more flexible terms due to increased social exposure. Interestingly, as masculinity scores declined across educational levels, indicators of psychological distress such as SIDAS, stress, and depression increased. University males, in particular, exhibited the highest levels of suicidal ideation and stress, suggesting that masculinity may act as a stabilizing identity structure during earlier educational stages, but becomes less effective or even detrimental as psychosocial demands increase.

Post hoc comparisons showed that masculinity was significantly higher among school students than those in college and university. However, school students also reported significantly better mental health outcomes, including lower SIDAS and depression and higher self-esteem and interpersonal coping. This could indicate that when masculinity is socially reinforced and unchallenged (as may occur in school), it serves a more functional role. In contrast, in higher education contexts where individual expression and emotional complexity are expected, rigid masculinity norms may conflict with emerging personal and academic stressors.

The current findings underscore a duality in the role of masculinity norms. On one hand, traditional masculinity appears linked to better coping, greater self-esteem, and lower suicidal ideation in adolescent males. On the other hand, its association with depression and its decline in protective power over time highlight the limitations of rigid gender norms in supporting long-term emotional well-being. This aligns with Connell's theory of hegemonic masculinity, where the dominant form of masculinity offers status but may come at the cost of emotional suppression, reluctance to seek help, and increased internalized stress (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005). These findings also support literature suggesting that masculinity norms can mask mental health symptoms in men, leading to delayed intervention or underreporting, especially in collectivist or patriarchal societies.

Implications

Overall, the findings indicate that masculinity norms significantly influence the mental health outcomes of men, functioning both as a buffer and a barrier depending on context, age, and institutional environment. Mental health interventions must be gender-sensitive, promoting flexible, emotionally expressive models of masculinity that retain confidence-building aspects while removing stigma from vulnerability. Future research should explore longitudinal changes in masculinity norms, their cultural specificity, and how redefining masculinity can support men's mental health across developmental stages.

Future Research Directions

Employing longitudinal designs could help trace developmental trajectories and clarify causality. Including qualitative data could enrich understanding of personal experiences behind the numbers. Exploring the impact of gender, socio-economic status and cultural background would offer a more nuanced understanding of psychological challenges across educational levels. Testing interventional models design to reduce distress and increases coping skills could provide practical applications of findings.

Conclusion

The study investigated the differences in psychological factors including muscularity perception, suicidal ideation, perceived helplessness, lack self-efficacy, emotional and behavioral symptoms, and depression across students at the school, college and university levels. The findings reveal significant development and educational stage related trends. School students reported higher levels of muscularity concern, externalizing behaviors, internalizing symptoms, and lack of self-efficacy high lightening early adolescents as a critical period for identity development and emotional regulation. In contrast, university students exhibited the highest level of suicidal ideation, depression, and perceived helplessness, pointing to the intensification of psychological distress in late adolescents and early adulthood.

These results underscore the importance of stage specific mental health interventions. For school students, the focus should be on building self-confidence, promoting healthy body image, and emotional regulation skills. For university students, efforts should be target stress management, resilience training, and assess to mental health resources to address the heightened risk of internalizing disorders. Overall, the study highlighted how psychological vulnerabilities evolve across educational stages, reinforcing the need for comprehensive mental

health educational and support systems that are tailored to the unique needs of development period.

References

- Addis, M. E. (2003). Men, masculinity, and the contexts of help seeking. *American Psychologist*, 58(1), 5-14. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.58.1.5>
- American College Health Association. (2022). *American College Health Association-National College Health Assessment*.
- Blumberg, S. J., Clarke, T. C., & Blackwell, D. L. (2015). Racial and ethnic disparities in men's use of mental health treatments (NCHS Data Brief No. 206). *National Centre for Health Statistics*, 1-8.
- Call, J. B., & Shafer, K. (2018). Gendered manifestations of depression and help seeking among men. *American Journal of Men's Health*, 12(1), 41-51. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1557988315623993>
- Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1983). A global measure of perceived stress. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 24(4), 385-396. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2136404>
- Connell, R. W., & Messerschmidt, J. W. (2005). Hegemonic masculinity: Rethinking the concept. *Gender & Society*, 19(6), 829-859. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891243205278639>
- Courtenay, W. H. (2000). Constructions of masculinity and their influence on men's well-being: A theory of gender and health. *Social Science & Medicine*, 50(10), 1385-1401. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(99\)00390-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(99)00390-1)
- Cummings, J. R., Wen, H., & Druss, B. G. (2014). Contextual socioeconomic status and mental health counseling use among US adolescents with depression. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 43(7), 1151-1162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-013-0047-8>
- Johnson, J. L., Oliffe, J. L., Kelly, M. T., Galdas, P., & Ogradniczuk, J. S. (2012). Men's discourses of help-seeking in the context of depression. *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 34(3), 345-361. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9566.2011.01372.x>
- King, T. L., Shields, M., Sojo, V., Milner, A., Spittal, M. J., & Pirkis, J. (2020). Conformity to masculine norms and suicidal thinking among young men in Australia. *BMC Psychiatry*, 20, 288. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-020-02678-y>

- Levant, R. F., & Wimer, D. J. (2020). The role of gender norms in predicting symptoms of depression and anxiety in men. *The Journal of Men's Studies*, 28(1), 85-95. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1060826519843162>
- Levant, R. F., Hall, R. J., & Rankin, T. J. (2013). Male Role Norms Inventory-Short Form (MRNI-SF): Development, confirmatory factor analytic investigation, and internal consistency reliability of a new measure of traditional masculinity ideologies. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 60(2), 228-238. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031545>.
- Mahalik, J. R., Locke, B. D., Ludlow, L. H., Diemer, M. A., Scott, R. P. J., Gottfried, M., & Freitas, G. (2003). Development of the Conformity to Masculine Norms Inventory. *Psychology of Men & Masculinity*, 4(1), 3-25. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1524-9220.4.1.3>
- Martin, L. A., Neighbors, H. W., & Griffith, D. M. (2013). The experience of symptoms of depression in men vs. women: Analysis of the National Comorbidity Survey Replication. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 70(10), 1100-1106. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2013.1985>
- Milner, A., Shields, M., King, T., & Currier, D. (2019). The influence of masculine norms and mental health on health literacy among men: Evidence from the Ten to Men Study. *American Journal of Men's Health*, 13(5), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1557988319873532>
- O'Neil, J. M. (2008). Summarizing 25 years of research on men's gender role conflict using the Gender Role Conflict Scale: New research paradigms and clinical implications. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 36(3), 358-445. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011000008317057>
- Pirkis, J., Spittal, M. J., Keogh, L., Mousaferiadis, T., & Currier, D. (2019). Masculinity and suicidal thinking. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 54(3), 319-327. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-018-1637-9>
- Radloff, L. S. (1977). The CES-D scale: A self-report depression scale for research in the general population. *Applied Psychological Measurement*, 1(3), 385-401. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014662167700100306>
- Rapee, R. M., Craske, M. G., Brown, T. A., & Barlow, D. H. (1996). Measurement of perceived control over anxiety-related events. *Behavior Therapy*, 27(2), 279-293. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-7894\(96\)80018-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0005-7894(96)80018-9)

- Salgado, D. M., Kuyper, L., & van den Brink, F. (2019). Men's health-risk and protective behaviors: The effects of masculinity and masculine norms. *Psychology of Men & Masculinities*, 20(2), 266-275. <https://doi.org/10.1037/men0000167>
- van Spijker, B. A., Batterham, P. J., Calear, A. L., Farrer, L., Christensen, H., Reynolds, J., & Kerkhof, A. J. F. M. (2014). The Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale (SIDAS): Community-based validation study of a new scale for the measurement of suicidal ideation. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 44(4), 408-419. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sltb.12084>
- Wong, Y. J., Ho, M. R., Wang, S. Y., & Miller, I. S. K. (2017). Meta-analyses of the relationship between conformity to masculine norms and mental health-related outcomes. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 64(1), 80-93. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000170>
- World Health Organization. (2022). *World mental health report: Transforming mental health for all*. WHO. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240049338>